

Survey of Madison Parks

Prior to beginning the survey, please read the following consent form and indicate your consent. The survey will require approximately 5 to 10 minutes. Thank you for your participation!

* Indicates required question

Animal Identification

Please provide your best answer for each of the following questions.

1. What animal is in the image? *

2. What animal is in the image? *

3. What animal is in the image? *

4. What animal is in the image? *

5. What animal is in the image? *

6. What animal is in the image? *

Animals

Please provide your best answer for each of the following questions.

7. Mark the statement that BEST describes how you feel about the animal in each of the numbered images living in the park you visited? Scroll right to see all response options.

*

Mark only one oval per row.

	I am happy they live at the park.	I think they are important for the park ecosystem.	I am concerned about their impact on human safety.	I am concerned they bring disease.	I think they are a nuisance.	I am unsure how I feel or I do not care.
Animal 1	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Animal 2	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Animal 3	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Animal 4	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Animal 5	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Animal						

Park Visit

Please provide your best answer for each of the following questions regarding your visit to the park.

8. What is the main reason you visited the park? *

Mark only one oval.

- Bird watching or Wildlife viewing
- Enjoy nature
- Exercise for fitness
- Nature photography
- Picnic
- Playground
- Play sports
- Walking or hiking
- Other: _____

9. Excluding the current visit, how many times did you visit the park within the last 12 months? *

Mark only one oval.

- 0 times
- 1 time
- 2 to 5 times
- 6 to 10 times
- 11 to 20 times
- greater than 20 times

10. Approximately how long did you stay at the park on this visit? *

Mark only one oval.

- less than 1 hour
- 1 to 2 hours
- greater than 2 hours

11. How far is the park from your residence? *

Mark only one oval.

- 1/4 mile to 1/2 mile
- 1/2 mile to 1 mile
- 1 mile to 3 miles
- 3 miles to 5 miles
- greater than 5 miles
- Other: _____

12. Please select the type of park that you visited most frequently in the last 12 months. *

Mark only one oval.

- Community Park (for example: Door Creek, Elver, or Olin Park)
- Conservation Park (for example: Edna Taylor, Owen, or Turville Point Conservation Park)
- Visit both community and conservation parks
- Unsure

Nature

Please provide your best answer for each of the following questions.

13. How often did you participate in the following during your childhood? Please select one of the following: "Never", "Rarely", "Sometimes", "Often", or "Very Often". Scroll right to see all response options.

*

Mark only one oval per row.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Very Often
Bird watching or Wildlife viewing	<input type="radio"/>				
Camping	<input type="radio"/>				
Canoeing or Kayaking	<input type="radio"/>				
Fishing	<input type="radio"/>				
Gardening	<input type="radio"/>				
Hiking	<input type="radio"/>				
Hunting	<input type="radio"/>				
Nature photography	<input type="radio"/>				
Picnicking	<input type="radio"/>				

14. How often did you participate in the following as an adult? Please select one of the following: "Never", "Rarely", "Sometimes", "Often", or "Very Often". Scroll right to see all response options. *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Very Often
Bird watching or Wildlife viewing	<input type="radio"/>				
Camping	<input type="radio"/>				
Canoeing or Kayaking	<input type="radio"/>				
Fishing	<input type="radio"/>				
Gardening	<input type="radio"/>				
Hiking	<input type="radio"/>				
Hunting	<input type="radio"/>				
Nature photography	<input type="radio"/>				
Picnicking	<input type="radio"/>				

15. I always think about how my actions affect the environment. *

Mark only one oval.

- Disagree strongly
- Disagree somewhat
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree somewhat
- Agree strongly

16. I take notice of wildlife wherever I am. *

Mark only one oval.

- Disagree strongly
- Disagree somewhat
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree somewhat
- Agree strongly

17. My relationship with nature is an important part of who I am. *

Mark only one oval.

- Disagree strongly
- Disagree somewhat
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree somewhat
- Agree strongly

18. I feel very connected to all living things and the earth. *

Mark only one oval.

- Disagree strongly
- Disagree somewhat
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree somewhat
- Agree strongly

19. My ideal vacation spot would be a remote, wilderness area. *

Mark only one oval.

- Disagree strongly
- Disagree somewhat
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree somewhat
- Agree strongly

20. My connection to nature and the environment is a part of my spirituality. *

Mark only one oval.

- Disagree strongly
- Disagree somewhat
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree somewhat
- Agree strongly

Park Visitor

Please provide your best answer for each of the following questions.

21. What is your zip code? *

22. What year were you born? *

23. What gender do you identify with? *

Mark only one oval.

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Do not wish to answer

24. What is the highest level of school you have completed? *

Mark only one oval.

- High school
- Two-year college graduate
- Four-year college graduate
- Graduate or professional degree
- Other
- Do not wish to answer

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